

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	0,383125	0,3542
Variance	0,00272332	0,00245903
Observations	16	15
Hypothesized	0	
df	29	
t Stat	1,58236799	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0,06220598	
t Critical one-tail	1,69912703	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0,12441196	
t Critical two-tail	2,04522964	

The results indicate no statistically significant difference between the means of Variable 1 and Variat

α = 0.05 in both one-tailed and two-tailed tests.